

Ten years on and still leading

Ten years ago, the Speedling system made its debut as a viable commercial method of forest seedling propagation. Those small beginnings at the old Wattle Research Institute (now the Institute for Commercial Forestry Research) blossomed rapidly. Within five years, Speedling accounted for nearly half of all forest seedlings required in South Africa.

Since those early days, not only has the face of forestry changed, but so has the concept of seedling propagation. The Speedling system heralded the entry of the specialist seedling nursery into the sphere of forestry. At last foresters could purchase better and cheaper seedlings than they could propagate themselves.

Why has the Speedling system had such a dramatic effect on forestry? Technically sound principles for plant growth coupled with obvious economic benefits. Timing was probably also important. Foresters were looking for nursery systems better than those they were using. The system has also been part of a wider change in forestry practice, e.g. a greater awareness of site/species interaction, the need for adequate site preparation and even fertilization.

Speedling remains the most popular choice of system for forestry seedlings.

Originally, seedlings were grown and had to be transplanted before the vigorous roots penetrated the trays. As is inevitable, certain difficulties outside the nursery meant that seedlings could not always be transplanted on due date. At the same time, the value of full container surface root pruning was being demonstrated by forest researchers. Styrodip was the result.

Management personnel are once again asking the nursery system to come up with a "breather" space for those occasions when seedlings cannot be transplanted. The current system of "holding" nurseries has been shown to create problems in the field. The prime factor is that holding nurseries by definition are for short term storage of seedlings. Unfortunately a significant number of seedlings are "held" for seven weeks or longer. Lack of nutrients, erratic or inadequate water and untrained management typical of these nurseries are surely the main problems.

Unfortunately, the current method of fairly fast early growth of seedlings does not easily allow for extended periods in the nursery. This is where good communication between nursery and forester is vital. Seedling growth is relatively easily manipulated provided that it is *not already on the seedling*. Any attempt to "hold" seedlings once they

A healthy wattle seedling, note the good root nodulation.

have reached transplantable stage must induce stress. While seedlings can recover from stress, this takes time. Once transplanted, time is often not available for seedlings to repair stress damage. Any further stress may result in mortality.

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Pine trees, living proof of the effectiveness of the Speedling system.

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What's new in Bedding Plants

Starke Ayres has on offer a wide range of new and exclusive products. These recommendations are based on extensive field trials and our observations at the overseas pack trials. The following are highly recommended for this season.

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3. Dianthus: the **Carpet** series is well-matched for performance and colour. From November the **Holiday** series will be available. These are superb bicolours, book now.

Leka, a new triploid marigold.

Continued from page 1

Ten years is not a long time in forestry. In fact the very first trees propagated in Speedling trays are just beginning to be felled. However, many millions of seedlings transplanted annually are living testimony to the system. It is appropriate that the Forest Nursery Workshop recently held in Pietermaritzburg should have reaffirmed the dominance of the Speedling system.

Busy lizzies, the Impact is tremendous.

4. Marigold: the triploids **Leka**, **Roca** and **Zenith** are unparalleled for garden performance. For Dwarf French Marigolds, consider **Hero**, certainly the best product in its class.
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6. Salvia: the new **Ryco** is an excellent bright red growing 25 cm. For the dwarfier kinds go for **Primco** with its dark foliage.
7. Verbena: go for the high germinating **Novallis** series, really an excellent product. Dwarf, compact and very free flowering.

Scarlet with eye, one in the verbena Novallis series.

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Bedding Plants

Bedding plants are showing signs of becoming the Cinderella of the seedling industry. A percentage of gardeners have traditionally bought seedlings rather than trying to raise their own. The modern trend is very definitely towards buying seedlings.

Modern gardeners tend to demand more instant results than gardeners of even ten years ago. The emphasis here is on larger seedlings and varieties quick into flower. There is even a trend towards seedlings already in flower.

New gardens tend to be smaller in area. This means that the average gardener no longer has to spread effort and money over large areas. Consequently, the emphasis is on fewer plants but with more striking characteristics. Ease of gardening is a major factor. Obviously transplanting bought seedlings is a lot easier and quicker than buying seed and starting from scratch. Modern breeding programmes are producing varieties far easier to care for than many of the old favourites. Disease resistance is a major factor.

These breeding programmes are in themselves pushing more gardeners to buying in bedding plants. The new hybrids tend to be fairly expensive, but in a small garden the accent is on performance. Buying in seedlings is the

obvious answer. On this point, it must be noted that modern vegetable hybrids are most readily available to gardeners as bedding plants also.

Improved production techniques and adapting methods best suited to the nursery are playing a large role in the bedding plant renaissance. The days of the bare root seedling and even the non-cellular punnet are strictly numbered. Economies of scale and a greater emphasis on product range linked to quality of product and choice of varieties are forcing the demise of the backyard nursery.

Specialisation is the word in the bedding plant industry just as the pot plant industry has split between wholesalers and retailers. New techniques such as the 'plug' system favour the specialist nursery, but in a symbiotic relationship with the retailer. On the other side, retailers are having to respond to customer demands for a wider product range and general garden information — especially after-sales care of plants.

Poor quality seedlings and indifferent varieties are discouraging to gardeners and retailers alike. Gardening is still the most popular hobby throughout the world. South Africans are no exception. Let us 'Green South Africa' in all the colours of the rainbow!

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TRANSPLANTING TECHNIQUES — the effect on yield

This one never made it — how many do you lose?

often occurring when the planting hole is too small because of poor field preparation. The common practice of 'firming in' by standing right next to the seedling (or on it!) is another major cause of this root growth.

Severe distortion of the roots during transplanting may physically break the roots. In this case the subsequent new roots will grow normally and only a slight delay in plant growth will result. Unfortunately, this seldom occurs. The severe contortions in the roots restrict movement of water and salts from the roots to the leaves, while at the same time restricting the movement of carbohydrates from the leaves to the roots. The result is poor growth, varying according to the degree of root distortion.

Unfortunately, there is nothing that can be done once the seedling has been transplanted. Very often the damage is not noticed until weeks (for vegetables) or even years (for forestry) later. A typical symptom of this problem in cabbage lands is a high percentage of heads harvested late or discarded entirely. It is a good practice to dig up a few discarded plants to check their root systems for signs of poor transplanting technique. In forestry, symptoms are typically only found when trees lodge and the root systems are dug up. Poor annual increment is seldom, if ever, attributed to these causes unless an academic investigation is in progress. A low rate of survival may also be caused by these root distortions. ▼

Periodically somebody looks at methods of transplanting and concludes that the techniques of the person transplanting seedlings can have a marked effect on root vigour and therefore final yield. Forestry has probably had a greater share of the investigations because of the greater economic implications of poor transplanting technique.

Two practices are most commonly observed. Bending of the roots is typically caused by forcing the roots into an inadequate planting hole. In forestry circles, this symptom is known as J-rooting and is just as apparent in vegetable and other seedlings. Long thin root plugs are more likely to be bent than the shorter inverted pyramid shapes. Bare root seedlings are seldom planted out without a high proportion of J-rooting.

The second symptom is a very characteristic flattened root form with roots tangled around each other and all growing out horizontally. This is caused by excessive force on the root plug,

OLD SEEDLINGS CUT YIELD POTENTIAL

The rapid swing towards the Speedling system of growing vegetable transplants has dramatically altered aspects of farm management. This popularity is due largely to the growth performance of these seedlings. Reduced management inputs, mainly because of greater field uniformity and earlier harvests, are another positive aspect.

Inevitably some hiccups will occur in such a widely used system. The physiological age of seedlings has long been known to affect their subsequent field growth and yield. While no clear cut recommendations can be given, it is evident that seedlings held for too long in the nursery lose their yield potential and growth uniformity. Single harvest vegetables such as cabbage and cauliflower are particularly affected. This reduction in yield is associated with

Yield potential of cabbage and cauliflower seedlings is reduced when seedlings are stressed by physiological ageing. Sensitive crops such as cauliflower and broccoli are most affected.

small heads in cabbage and 'buttoning' of cauliflowers. Both are symptoms of a severe stress to the plant. Multiple harvest vegetables such as tomatoes and peppers usually show a reduced and delayed first harvest, but may recover later in the season. Little is known about onions, but an increase in bolting, splitting and multiple bulbs can be expected.

At maturity, seedlings which have been stressed by physiological ageing generally show little, if any, root growth from the root plug. They are very slow to develop in the field because growth is arrested while adventitious roots form above the plug. This would suggest that the roots are directly involved in causing

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the stress. However, changes in the top growth cannot be discounted.

The exact physiological cause of seedling ageing is unknown. Ageing appears to be associated with competition between adjacent plants for light. Under average summer nursery conditions, crucifer seedlings take about four weeks (Model 200) to six weeks (Model 128) before they are ready for transplanting. The graph shows how serious the loss in yield potential can be if seedlings are delayed in the nursery.

Until more accurate estimates can be made, seedlings should preferably be transplanted as soon as the roots have formed an adequate root plug. If seedling nutrition has been adequate and correctly balanced, this stage should coincide with the touching of the leaves of adjacent seedlings. This would be the optimum time for transplanting. Delays of 15–20 percent of the seedling age (about 5–10 days in summer) do not appear to have a large effect on yield potential.

There will always be times when delayed transplanting cannot be prevented. Cold storage of seedlings is probably the best available option provided seedlings are fully revived before transplanting. Otherwise a reduced nutrition and watering programme should be applied, being careful not to overstress seedlings. A revival programme should be implemented 2–5 days before transplanting.

PONGOLA TOMATO SYMPOSIUM

A Tomato Symposium is to be held by the Seedling Growers Association of SA in Pongola on Thursday 3 November 1988 from 09h30 to an evening braai at 17h30. The venue is Johan Pienaar's farm, plot 120 on the north coast road from Durban, 15 km from Pongola. AA signs will be displayed.

The Seedling Growers Association of SA is a national body of member nurseries with a strong commitment to research into the production of better seedlings and reduced costs. It is also committed to extension and the release of information to nurserymen and farmers. The Seedling Growers Association believes in presenting a service of this kind to their members and community of farmer-clients. Speakers are recognised experts

with experience in their fields. 'It's unusual to get together a collection of such competent speakers on so many aspects of a single subject — tomatoes', says Mark Laing, Plant Pathologist, University of Natal, Pietermaritzburg.

The organisers emphasise that all lectures are designed to be suitable for all farmers. Topics will address tomato farm management, cultivar breeding and evaluation, news from USA tomato growers and problems with pests and diseases. An extensive demonstration trial of tomato cultivars can be viewed with the opportunity of discussing the merits of each cultivar.

The cost is R70 per person which includes lectures, teas, lunch, field trial examination and discussion, and the evening braai.

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GROWING MEDIA — where quality begins

Ever since gardeners first started growing plants in containers, the problems of providing a growing medium suited to the plant's requirements have caused many a headache. The advent of soil science and more sophisticated, accurate and available means of measuring nutrient levels and various physical qualities was seen as the answer to the growing medium nightmare.

Unfortunately, classical soil science principles do not seem to fit experiences in container production. Nutrient solubility curves over the pH range for mineral and organic soils have been used to justify favouring certain media mixes over others. In particular, liming principles are based on these solubility curves. This has left us with a wealth of recommended pH levels based on numerous trials. In spite of these recommendations, experience shows a far wider range in acceptable pH. Organic media can be roughly split into two basic categories. Lower pH (pH 3,0–4,5) for 'acid loving' plants and higher pH (pH 4,0–6,5) for virtually all other plants. This suggests that pH in itself is not a major factor, particularly

when vermiculite, a popular inorganic medium, has a range of pH 8,0–9,5.

What then are the criteria for determining the quality of a container growing medium? Unfortunately researchers have only just started freeing themselves from assuming that what occurs in soils also occurs in a container medium. However, great strides are being made in determining the physical characteristics of suitable media. What must not be forgotten is that a medium suited to one specific environment and management system

may not suit another nursery. For this reason, many very different media are available. They range from pure organics such as peat and composted bark to inorganics such as perlite, vermiculite and rockwool through to various proprietary foam or sponge-like materials.

Characteristics common to all container growing media are their light weight, good aeration and water-holding capacity linked to drainage, low salt status and generally high cation exchange capacity. Increasingly important is our understanding of the link between media characteristics and nutrition on plant growth. In particular, the importance of trace elements is becoming better understood.

Nurserymen entering the industry from other disciplines often express surprise that plant production has not yet been defined and refined into a factory-type of operation. Even a cursory glance at the many factors which affect plant growth show that it is a highly complex field. Hats off to those with green fingers who not only produce high quality plants, but also do it regularly.

Pine bark — decorative as well as an excellent quality growing medium.

TRAY TREATMENTS

— pros and cons for vegetables

Styrodip is well known to forestry seedling growers but is not as well known to the vegetable seedling growers. A common misconception is that Styrodip acts by coating the tray and thus physically preventing root penetration. Styrodip activity is, in fact, a chemical root pruning and it is this activity which prevents roots growing into the fabric of the tray.

Why should seedling roots be pruned? Primarily to aid healthy, active root tip development and secondarily to prevent the formation of a 'root cage' which leads to root binding.

A mass of roots showing on the outer surface of the root plug is, in fact, not a desirable feature. Chemical root pruning at the growing medium/cell wall interface will prevent this typical container-type of root form. These typically large roots have few active root tips, tend to cause compaction in the root plug thus making the plugs difficult to extract, as well as being exposed to desiccation when extracted and packed for delivery to the farm.

Tests have shown no adverse effects on seedling growth due to Styrodip activity. In general, a slight improvement in growth is noted. This

agrees with other tests whereby root pruning in container plants may improve plant growth by up to 15 percent.

Another advantage of using Styrodip is the ease of extraction of seedlings from the trays. It is common to see seedlings forced out of trays with a 'popping machine'. If excessive force is required, not only are seedlings damaged, but trays are also broken and the packing process is greatly extended.

Current usage is a Styrodip treatment approximately once annually for quick crops (flowers and vegetables) and between every crop for slow or particularly vigorous rooting crops (forestry and pastures). Particular care needs to be taken to ensure that the solution is adequately agitated before and during tray treatment, otherwise the sticker emulsion will be applied without the active ingredient. Adequate root pruning activity is seldom obtained routinely unless trays have been treated from new. Minute particles of dirt in the cracks prevents Styrodip penetrating these cracks, thereby allowing fine roots to grow between the beads of polystyrene.

Research is an on-going process to

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WEEDS — A REGULAR CURSE

Warrick Nelson

Weeds in a nursery are usually considered a minor irritation and seldom become a serious threat to profitability. This is a dangerous attitude if plant quality is to be maintained.

Apart from direct competition for light, water, nutrients and general growing space, weeds are typically alternate hosts to many pests and diseases. Careful monitoring of aphid and red spider mite populations on weeds in and around the nursery has proven to be a useful early warning system to apply control measures in the nursery crop. Unfortunately, this technique is seldom extended to control measures applied to the weeds, or better still full eradication of the weeds. No available host plants means a much

A serious infestation of *Cardamine flexuosa*. Up to twenty weed plants per plug were counted. Note the masses of little white flowers.

The characteristic leaf shape and rapid seed set are the guides to identifying Flick seed bittercress.

more difficult transition for pests from outside the nursery onto the nursery crop.

Direct competition between crop and weed means both plants are stressed and more susceptible to diseases. Downy mildew is a common disease in seedling nurseries. Overcrowding of seedlings, especially with weed plants pushing in creates ideal conditions for survival of this disease while also making effective control more difficult.

Weed infested seedling trays are hardly a sight to inspire confidence in any nurseryman. While *Oxalis* is commonly found in nurseries and can become a serious problem in longer term crops, it is not normally a serious problem in seedling nurseries.

However, a recent introduction to the seedling nurseryman's problems is Bittercress or Flick seed bittercress (*Cardamine* sp.). In particular, *Cardamine flexuosa* has caused serious problems in a number of nurseries. Being a close relative of cabbages, disease potential is obvious.

Flick seed bittercress is an indigenous weed endemic to damp, shady habitats. The most likely source of contamination in a nursery is in stream water used for irrigation, seed infested mud on shoes or car tyres or even importing infested plants from other nurseries! This weed is typically an insignificant pale green leafy plant growing under tables and other damp, shady areas of the nursery. It is easily confused with chick weed and a number of similar weeds. However, the mechanism of flicking seed two or more metres out makes contamination on the tables merely a matter of time.

The fast reproductive rate makes this weed a problem even in short-term vegetable seedlings. If the growing medium is contaminated with seed before or during tray filling, the weed easily has enough time to grow and set seed. The habit of flicking mature seed also means quick contamination of clean trays placed within three metres of mature weed plants. Plants barely 20 mm tall have been found with mature seed!

Cardamine flexuosa is probably only a relatively new weed to seedling nurseries because of the youth of most nurseries. Regular and effective weed control in and around the nursery is the only solution. I have observed this weed in nurseries from the Western Cape through to the Transvaal Lowveld. Be aware, this insignificant plant could cost you lots of money. ▼

Geharde Speedling-plantjies volgens bestelling gekweek:

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PLUGGING SEEDLINGS — a logical extension

Pick up virtually any horticultural magazine from the USA and chances are that there will be an article dealing with seedling plugs. Although very closely related and utilising similar concepts, plug seedlings are not the same as those produced in Speedling trays by most local nurseries.

Plug seedlings are typically very small (Model 338 and smaller), are usually produced by specialist nurseries and are grown on by retail nurseries after transplanting. Flowering pot plants and larger seedlings in cellular or open punnets are typically grown from plug seedlings. A uniform stand of seedlings in the typical six or 12 seedling punnet is virtually guaranteed.

Why have plugs become so popular? The traditional method of starting seedlings in an open punnet and pricking out into the final container is slow, inefficient and often results in non-uniform stands. The plug system has revolutionised the retail nursery industry in much the same way as Speedling did for vegetable farmers.

South African nurseries are just beginning to use the system. Typically,

Plugging away at profits the Speedling way.

seed is sown into a Model 338 Speedling tray where seedlings are grown until they are ready for transplanting to a larger container. The capital requirement for seed sowing machinery, controlled germination and growth facilities suggest the development of a specialist wholesale nursery.

Implementation of a plug seedling system will simplify operations for most nurseries. Once ordered, the nurseryman only needs to be prepared for transplanting the finished plugs into the punnets used for final sales.

This is far quicker with plug seedlings than the traditional pricked out seedling and growth to saleable stage is very fast. Even better for simplifying nursery operations is that the seedling punnet currently used need not be discarded. Of course, you may wish to extend the benefits of the Speedling system to your customers by also retailing seedlings in Speedling trays.

While plugging has become most popular for bedding plants, the concept has definite advantages for the forest seedling industry as well as ornamental plant propagation. The major advantages of plugging are the quality control during nursery growth and optimisation of space, inputs and facilities. Any plant normally displaying erratic germination and growth (including rooting of cuttings) is a candidate for the plugging extension to the Speedling system. ▼

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EDITOR'S VIEW

At the recent Forest Nursery Workshop, a plastic tube or insert system was suggested as the ultimate for nursery seedling propagation. Ease of sorting into size classes is the major benefit, as well as total lack of penetration of roots into trays. Even-sized seedlings are expected to give uniform plantations, however research has yet to show such a correlation. Current nursery practises involve discarding runts when a seedling order is pulled and despatched. With efficient size grading in the nursery, the chances of these runts and off-types ending up in a single compartment are increased. Progress in the field of root pruning to eliminate the formation of a "root cage" appears to have been forgotten.

Horticultural technology is developing at a rapid rate. The concept of artificial seed produced by gel encapsulating somatic embryos has barely moved out of the academic literature and already varieties of plants are commercially available. Are our efforts at selecting forest clones on their rootability going to be remembered in five years time? More importantly, are nursery systems specifically designed for rooted cutting production going to be required? Mechanisation in tissue culture and gel encapsulation techniques shows potential to replace classical clonal propagation methods.

Nutrition, quality parameters of growing media and the importance of pH, electrical conductivity and osmotic potential in irrigation water are receiving far greater attention by researchers. In particular, the requirement for trace elements is becoming far better understood. The links between pH and nutrient availability in growing media, taken over from soil science, are being broken and a clearer picture of container plant nutrition is being obtained. At last we are making headway in understanding the physical factors affecting containerised plants.

Bedding and ornamental plant producers in general have been largely unaffected by the effect the Speedling system has had on other nurseries. It is a healthy sign that this sector is beginning to take advantage of the Speedling system. In particular, a movement towards plug seedlings as a step in the production of seedling punnets is occurring.

Landscapes are likely to benefit greatly by a greater availability of suitable transplants from the Speedling system. In the March 1988 issue, the use of Speedling plugs for lawn establishment was illustrated. Other landscaping plants, in particular ground covers of all types, can be more efficiently propagated, transported and transplanted. The unique root pruning system using Styrodip helps ensure that transplants develop vigorous, healthy root systems in the ground.

The wide range of Speedling tray types available in South Africa ensure the maximum application of this efficient plant propagation system. It is unfortunate that so many nurserymen are still not aware of the full potential of Speedling — even in specialised nursery practises.

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Die kostes verbonde aan die plasing van artikels in beide Engels en Afrikaans is ontsaglik duur. Lesers wat 'n vertaling van enige artikel benodig is egter welkom om daarvoor aan te vra. Stuur 'n self-geadresseerde koevert met die nodige posseël aan ons en dui duidelik aan watter artikel u benodig. ▼

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Code/Kode

Business e.g. — forestry, vegetable farmer, seedling grower etc.
Besigheid bv. — bosbou, groenteboer, saailing kweker ens.

SEEDLING NEWS

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New Seed Products Update

New hybrid cabbages have been released fairly frequently over the past few years. These two will take the market by storm!

Crystal Star has the flavour to take top awards on the markets. Best suited to late summer and autumn harvesting, it is the quickest maturing in its class. Resistance to cabbage yellows, excellent tolerance to black rot and ability to be held in the land all make this variety a winner. Suited for medium to high density planting, optimum sowing period is October to January and a bit later in warm areas.

Balloon will blow your mind for autumn and early winter harvests. At 15–20 days earlier than **Green Coronet**, the current favourite, this variety will put money in your pocket quicker. Excellent black rot tolerance and the high quality heads expected from KUDU varieties, this is a variety not to be trifled with. Optimal sowing time is December to February and a bit later in warm areas.

Chinese cabbages are making their mark on the local market. Traditionally grown for ships chandlers, these cabbages are increasingly popular with restaurants and better households which are proud of their salads. Exceptionally fast (at 55–60 days from transplanting), **Hero** is the best we've seen. In addition, high density planting (50–55 000 per hectare) and 1,8–2,2 kg heads,

Hero gives excellent returns. All year production is possible, but cooler regions may have problems with bolting in spring.

Hot Mexican, Portuguese and Indian dishes rely on good quality chilli peppers. **Pendant** produces uniform fruit already well accepted for the local Indian market. The deep red fruit is decorative as well as very pungent. Not for the delicate constitution! Good wind resistance makes this variety an exceptional performer on the coast.

Elite is fast becoming the standard against which other zucchinis are measured. The uniform, nearly cylindrical fruits are a pre-packer's delight. Their fresh colour and obvious quality move them out of supermarkets fast. Compact vines, clean picking and higher yield potential make **Elite** the farmer's friend. Moderate anti-aphid silvering aids in preventing virus infection. Whether you say zucchini, courgette or baby marrow, say **Elite**. ▼

SAAD EN DIE LEWE

Die wals word 'n vastrap

Minder as vyftien jaar gelede was boere erg ontstoke toe die eerste baster koolsaad op die toneel verskyn het:

'Kyk na die prys', het hulle uitgeroep, 'die mark sal bastersaad nooit aanvaar nie. Ons sal bankrot gaan as ons soveel vir ons saad moet betaal!'

Deesdae word boere, wat nog steeds ernstig na die ou oopbestuifde koolkultivars kyk, as ietwat 'agter' deur hulle bure beskou.

Basters is gewis nie goedkoop nie, maar dat die eindresultaat die hoë prys meer as regverdig is nie altemit nie.

Die eerste mieliebasters is nagenoeg veertig jaar gelede vrygestel. Soos verwag kon word, was prys die belangrikste oorweging by baie boere en is die verhoogde opbrengspotensiaal geheel en al geïgnoreer. En waar is die oopbestuifde varieteite vandag?

Natuurlik is verbeterde saadkultivars nie die enigste faktor wat 'n rol speel nie.

Meer aandag aan die ander produksieinsette en bestuurstechnieke sowel as die bemerking van die oes is ook noodsaaklik om winste te verhoog. Insetkoste styg om munt te slaan uit die hoër opbrengspotensiaal van 'n spesifieke baster. Gevolglik handhaaf saadkoste dieselfde klein persentasie van die totale produksiekoste soos voorheen.

Watter ander gewasse is beïnvloed deur die praktiese benutting van basterkrag?

In Suid-Afrika word nie baie groente deur middel van basterkultivars geproduseer nie. Die plaaslike neiging tot ekstensiewe boerderypraktyke, selfs in die geval van intensiewe gewasse soos groente, het veroorsaak dat die

aanvraag vir basterkultivars nie so hoog is soos in ander lande nie. Die gebruik van 'n baster waarborg ook nie 'n beter opbrengs in alle gevalle nie. Tamaties en spanspekke is 'n goeie voorbeeld in hierdie verband. Van die beste kultivars van hierdie gewasse is oopbestuifde varieteite, terwyl basters net aan die behoeftes van 'n spesifieke mark voldoen. Die druk op saadmaatskappye met hul eie teelprogram is egter so groot dat daar vandag 'n groot verskeidenheid basters bestaan waarvan die produsent kan kies.

Wat van die toekoms?

Nog voordat meer gewasse deur die benutting van basterkrag opgegradeer kan word, word nuwe tegnieke ontwikkel wat die planteler nog beter in staat stel om nuwe, verbeterde gewaskultivars te produseer. Sulke tegnieke het dit byvoorbeeld moontlik gemaak om 'n rooi Sjinese kool met 'n buitengewone groeikrag te ontwikkel. Maar die vraag mag wel gevra word: 'Waarvoor nou eintlik soiets?'

Die isolasie van genes wat 'n hoë mate van weerstand teen siektes, insekte en chemiese middels, veral onkruidodders, bied, is reeds die orde van die dag. Hierdie genes kan van een plant na 'n ander, verwante, en selfs heeltemal onverwante, plant oorgeplant word. Hierdie tegnieke, beter bekend as 'genetic engineering' word ook reeds kommersieel benut.

Wat kan die vooruitstrewende boer van vandag doen om sy voorsprong te behou? Die steeds toenemende behoefte aan spesialisasie maak dit nie makliker vir die tradisionele gesinsboer om by te bly nie.

Is dit dan die begin van die einde van die klein, onafhanklike boer?

Nie noodwendig nie. Die vaardighede en gespesialiseerde kennis wat vir die hedendaagse moderne boerdery al hoe meer noodsaaklik word, word deesdae toenemend deur konsultante aangebied. Starke Ayres was nog altyd 'n voorstander van die filosofie dat naverkoopdiens en die produk wat hulle bemark hand in hand gaan. Namate die saadbedryf meer en meer ingewikkeld word, word die diensaspek al hoe belangriker, en die blote verspreiding van nuwe, verbeterde saadkultivars nie meer goed genoeg nie. Die produsent sal sy prioriteite moet kan identifiseer, al die kultivars tot sy beskikking daarvolgens kan evalueer, en toegang hê tot al die inligting met betrekking tot die jongste saadtegnologie, ten einde te verseker dat sy besigheid lewensvatbaar bly.

Sy keuse van 'n bekwame konsultant sal bepaal of hy die paal haal!

WHITE ROCK

White Rock — exceptional quality even in the hot months.

Late summer and autumn cauliflower production is normally difficult. Fortunately **White Rock** has proven adaptable to these harsh conditions and responds with exceptionally high quality curds. The rather small framed plants with upright foliage have often been cause for concern, until the deep, firm and finely textured pure white curds form. The upright leaves protect the curds from the harsh rays of the sun. An average head size of 1 kg maturing 85–95 days from transplanting is normal following October to February sowing. As with all cauliflowers, any check during growth can cause disappointing results. In general, 30–40% more fertilizer than required for cabbages should be given.

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